

Composite Hydrogels of Alkyl Functionalized Gellan Gum Derivative and Hydroxyapatite/Tricalcium Phosphate Nanoparticles as Injectable Scaffolds for bone Regeneration

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An alkyl functionalized gellan gum derivative is here used to produce hydrogels containing hydroxyapatite and tricalcium phosphate nanoparticles as injectable nanostructured scaffolds for bone regeneration. The amphiphilic nature of the polysaccharide derivative along with its thermotropic behavior and ionotropic crosslinking features make possible to produce injectable bone mimetic scaffolds that can be used to release viable cells and osteoinductive biomolecules. The influence of different nanoparticles concentration on the rheological and physicochemical properties of the injectable systems is studied. It is found that the presence of inorganic nanoparticles reinforces the 3D hydrated polymeric networks without influencing their injectability but improving the physicochemical properties of ionotropic crosslinked hydrogels produced with two different curing media. Preliminary cytocompatibility tests performed with murine preosteoblast cells revealed that gellan gum based hydrogels can safely encapsulate viable cells. Loading and release experiments for dexamethasone and stromal cell-derived factor-1 demonstrate the drug delivery features of the obtained injectable systems.

1. Introduction

Treatment of bone defect lesions can be addressed with minimally invasive techniques, with the aim of facilitating defect filling and reducing surgical impact.^[1] Polysaccharides represent an adequate choice for the design of injectable biomaterials due

to their appropriate physical, rheological, and biological properties and the possibility of forming hydrophilic and biocompatible matrices.^[2–4] However, once injected, these biomaterials should be able to acquire sufficient mechanical strength thanks to the action of specific local stimuli, capable of triggering a physical crosslinking or, thanks to biocompatible procedures, of obtaining a chemical crosslinking in situ.^[5,6] Ionotropic polysaccharides can be physically crosslinked in the presence of bivalent cations found into the site of injection or specifically generated or added with the injected material. Among them, alginate and gellan gum have been widely applied as injectable crosslinkable materials for bone tissue engineering (TE).^[2,7–9]

Gellan gum (GG) is a linear anionic polysaccharide with tetrasaccharidic repeating units consisting of $[\text{D-Glc}(\beta 1 \rightarrow 4)\text{-D-GlcA}(\beta 1 \rightarrow 4)\text{-D-Glc}(\beta 1 \rightarrow 4)\text{-L-Rha}(\alpha 1 \rightarrow 3)]_n$, unmodified high molecular weight GG

has a gelation temperature too high to be practically suitable for injection at body temperature, for this reason several GG derivatives have been proposed with the aim to decrease temperature of aggregation and/or to improve aqueous solubility without losing thermal responsiveness and ionotropic crosslinking properties.^[10–13] Alkyl functionalized GG derivatives, produced from low molecular weight deacetylate GG batches, showed sharp gelation temperatures below 37 °C, still maintaining optimal viscoelastic properties if compared to unmodified GG.^[14,15] The typical ionotropic gelation and the formation of hydrophobic coils allow to obtain injectable fluid precursors with tunable viscosity that undergo rapid in situ gelation and can be used as a vehicle for both cells and osteoinductive agents, such as inorganic nanofillers or bioactive compounds. These systems can be administered to fill bone defects through minimally invasive surgical procedures without the need for external curing (e.g., UV irradiation) or to undergo a chemical crosslinking whose times must be precisely regulated. Recent approaches to bone tissue engineering focus on the design of acellular osteoinductive scaffolds^[16–18] in which inorganic nanofillers are incorporated into the injectable formulation to improve mechanical performance and impart osteoinductive properties. Such colloidal particles, in the case of polysaccharide hydrogels, interact on

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Figure 1. Schematic representation of a) GG-C₁₈ repetitive units and b) hydrogels preparation procedure.

their surface with hydrophilic macromolecules establishing weak interactions thus strengthening the entanglement of the polymeric network.^[19,20] Inorganic nanoparticles consisting of hydroxyapatite (HAp) and β -tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP), due to their similarity with the inorganic compounds of the natural bone extracellular matrix, are widely used, often in combination, as an osteoinductive nanostructured dopant for the design of mechanically performing scaffolds.^[21–27] Here, a gellan gum octadecyl derivative (named as GG-C₁₈) having favorable thermorheological profile, was used to formulate composite nanostructured injectable hydrogels by producing aqueous dispersion in the presence of HAp and β -TCP. The effect of different concentrations of inorganic nanofillers on the thermo-gelation properties and injectability of the hydrogel precursors was investigated by means of rheological measurements. Iontropic gelation was performed in two different curing media to investigate the influence of both cation nature and nanofiller presence on the main physicochemical and viscoelastic properties of the composite hydrogels. MC3T3-E1 preosteoblastic cells were encapsulated in a hydrogel precursor at room temperature and the constructs were cultured for a period of 21 days to study cell viability. Finally, the possibility of using injectable systems for the delivery of two bioactive molecules widely used in bone tissue engineering such as Dexamethasone and stromal cell-derived factor-1 (SDF-1) was investigated. In particular, Dexamethasone is a synthetic glucocorticoid with known osteoinductive effects on mesenchymal stem cell differentiation,^[28,29] while SDF-1 is a potent chemokine, which stimulates the recruitment of stem cells in both normal and damaged tissues interacting with the CXC type-4 chemokine receptor (CXCR4) stimulating cell migration and accelerating regeneration.^[30,31]

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Hydrogel Production

The association between HAp and β -TCP was chosen as a dopant for GG-C₁₈ dispersions in the light of their known bone mimetic properties in order to improve mechanical performances of hydrogel scaffolds. In fact, it is known that calcium phosphate nanoparticles, due to their colloidal nature, sustain a better osteoinductive activity and an improved integration with host tissues in TE approaches.^[32,33] The dispersion of GG derivative (**Figure 1a**) and nanoparticles was achieved through direct sterilization of powders and water using an autoclave procedure (121 °C for 15 min) as reported in **Figure 1b**.

The high temperature reached during the process increases the fluidity of the dispersion due to the thermal sensitivity of the starting polysaccharide derivative and brings the system into a sol phase which probably allows an easy dispersion of the nanoparticulate dopants.

After sterilization, hot dispersions ($\cong 40$ °C) were withdrawn with a sterile syringe and injected into the cell culture inserts. After cooling to room temperature, the coil-to-helix transition, together with the hydrophobic interactions that are established between the alkyl chains of GG-C₁₈, leads to the obtainment of structured hydrogels.

2.2. Rheological Characterization

Thermal rheological properties of GG-C₁₈, GG-C₁₈ 1% NPs, and GG-C₁₈ 10% NPs aqueous dispersions were analyzed and compared (**Figure 2a–c**).

Figure 2. Temperature dependence of storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') during cooling process for a) GG-C₁₈, b) GG-C₁₈ 1%NPs, and c) GG-C₁₈ 10%NPs 3% w/v aqueous dispersions. Experiments were performed at 0.159 Hz and 1.5% of strain. d) GG-C₁₈, e) GG-C₁₈ 1%NPs, and f) GG-C₁₈ 10%NPs 3% w/v aqueous dispersions monitored between low stress (10 Pa) and high stress (1000 Pa) at 25 °C. g) Stress-dependent viscosity of GG-C₁₈, GG-C₁₈ 1%NPs, and GG-C₁₈ 10%NPs at 25 °C. h) Extrusion of GG-C₁₈ 10%NPs hydrogel from syringe at room temperature.

All the samples showed a coil-to-helix transition temperature between 50 and 35 °C confirming the behavior observed for the GG-C₁₈ derivative in our previous experiment.^[15] G'' - G' crossover point increased with the presence of nanoparticles being 37 °C for GG-C₁₈ and 40 and 42 °C for GG-C₁₈ 1% NPs and GG-C₁₈ 10% NPs respectively, thus suggesting that this phenomenon could be related to the structuring effect of HAP and β -TCP nanoparticles. Probably, the interactions between the polar surfaces of the nanoparticles and GG-C₁₈ that occur during the cooling process facilitate the entanglement of the polymer chains and the coil-to-helix transition. Injectability and

recovery of mechanical properties of hydrogels were assayed by performing yield stress experiments. Recovery test, performed at 25 °C, showed that strength of hydrogels increased sensibly with the increasing nanoparticles concentration (G' increased from 200 to 400 Pa for undoped GG-C₁₈ and GG-C₁₈ 10% Np) and that after the stress application, hydrogel character was lost with an intensity increasing with the increased nanoparticles concentration (GG-C₁₈ 1% NPs, GG-C₁₈ 10% NPs) and then fully recovered after stress was reduced (Figure 2d–f). All samples showed yield stress values greater than 500 Pa at 25 °C, thus suggesting that these systems could be conveniently injected

Figure 3. Frequency sweep experiments performed in the range 0.0628–62.8 rad s⁻¹ at a constant strain of 1.5% on GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels incubated in a) DMEM or cured in CaCl₂ 0.1 M for 1 h and incubated in b) DMEM.

laparoscopically, while having optimal retention at the application site.^[34] The yield stress analysis showed an increase in pseudoplastic behavior by increasing the concentration of nanoparticles in polymer dispersion 3% w/v (Figure 2g,h) as demonstrated by the decrease in the yield stress point. This result means that the presence of nanoparticles facilitates the extrusion of the polymer dispersion from the needle.

Thermal rheological analysis, yield stress and recovery, taken together, have suggested that both the undoped and doped formulations have suitable rheological properties to be injected into the tissue defect being able to rapidly recover their mechanical properties at 37 °C and confirmed the structuring effect performed by adding Nps.

Once injected, GG hydrogels are sensible to the ionic strength of the external medium undergoing ionotropic gelation in the presence of both mono and divalent cations. While monovalent cations induce the gelation of the aqueous dispersions only by reducing the electrostatic repulsion between the carboxylate groups of the polysaccharide, divalent cations create also saline bonds between the macromolecules. For this reason, the latter are used to produce more structured hydrogels with higher storage modulus (G').

Mechanical performances of hydrogels could be affected by the presence of K⁺, Na⁺, and Ca²⁺ ions. Several strategies have been designed to obtain locally induced ionotropic crosslinking, capable of improving the mechanical performance of the designed materials. To detect the effect of ion induced crosslinking, mechanical–rheological profile of GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels was evaluated comparing curing procedures by using DMEM buffer and CaCl₂ crosslinking. After 1 h of polymerization, G' values for CaCl₂ treated hydrogels are nearly one order of magnitude higher than DMEM crosslinked hydrogels, according to the stronger effect of Ca²⁺ in coordinating GG-C₁₈ carboxylate groups (Figure 3).

A significant increase in the elastic modulus (G') of the hydrogels was recorded with increasing the concentration of nanoparticles for both crosslinking media, further confirming that the high surface area of the nanoparticles results in the forma-

tion of weak interactions (mainly hydrogen bonds) with the GG-C₁₈ polysaccharide backbone which helps to compact the hydrogels.^[21]

Higher differences compared to the undoped hydrogel were observed for the DMEM buffer probably due to the lower degree of crosslinking which “unmasks” the effect of the nanoparticles on the viscoelastic properties of the samples.

Interestingly, after 14 days of incubation, DMEM cured nanoparticle doped hydrogels improved their elastic characteristics (as it is evident from the significant increase in G' values for both GG-C₁₈ 1% NP and GG-C₁₈ 10% NP) while GG-C₁₈ recorded a significant decrease compared to the G' values recorded after 1 h of crosslinking (Figure 3a).

This behavior once again confirms the important role of nanoparticles in improving the structuring of hydrogels. Clearly, the slow dissolution of the β -TCP nanoparticles results in a gradual release of calcium ions which presumably strengthen the hydrated 3D network.

This trend is not observable for the hydrogels cured with CaCl₂ 0.1 M as the G' values are more influenced by the depletion of the Ca²⁺ ions “curing” from the polymeric network which are exchanged with the monovalent ions present in higher concentration than those of bivalents in DMEM^[35] (Figure 3b).

In other words, for these samples, the rate at which Ca²⁺ ions are lost during incubation is greater than the rate at which they are replaced by the dissolution of the β -TCP nanoparticles.

It is however interesting to note that the G' values, after 14 days of incubation for samples containing nanoparticles, are very similar regardless of the curing medium.

A significant improvement in the mechanical performance of the hydrogels can be expected if a prolonged in situ generation of Ca²⁺ ions is achieved; on the other hand, an initial crosslinking of the hydrogel obtained from the co-injection of a calcium chloride solution may not be sufficient to sustain a prolonged improvement in mechanical performance.

Internal gelation procedures^[36,37] capable of sustaining the prolonged release of Ca²⁺, could allow to maintain sufficient mechanical properties for a potential osteochondral regeneration.

Figure 4. DSC and TGA curves of GG-C₁₈ (black); GG-C₁₈ 1% NPs (red); GG-C₁₈ 10% NPs (blue). Top right shows a magnification of the DSC curve (230–260 °C), while bottom right shows a magnification of the TGA curve (210–260 °C).

2.3. Physicochemical Characterization

DSC and TGA analyses confirmed that HAp and β -TCP nanoparticles have a compacting effect on the 3D hydrated network as the degradation temperature of GG-C₁₈ increases (albeit slightly) in the presence of the nanoparticle dopant compared to the starting sample GG-C₁₈ (Figure 4). In particular, a significant increase in degradation temperature was observed only for the hydrogel containing the highest amount of nanoparticles (GG-C₁₈ 10% NPs) while the TGA analysis revealed that both samples containing nanoparticles show a degradation temperature higher than GG-C₁₈ (Figure 4).

Freeze-dried GG-C₁₈ based samples, which were crosslinked in CaCl₂ 0.1 M or DMEM, appeared macroscopically as dried sponges with irregular structures on the micrometric scale as can be seen from the SEM micrographs shown in Figure 5. Submicrometric white clusters can be seen based on the increase in the concentration of nanoparticles, thus demonstrating the efficiency of direct dispersion during the sterilization procedure. As expected, these structures are particularly visible for GG-C₁₈ 10% NP (Figure 5g–i) and are not observable in the GG-C₁₈ hydrogel. The micrometric structure of the 3D dried polymer networks varied with the treatment in DMEM and in CaCl₂.

Indeed, the samples obtained after crosslinking in DMEM (Figure 5b,e,h) appeared more porous than the untreated samples (Figure 5a,d,g), while the crosslinking in calcium chloride generated more compact structures.

This behavior is attributable to the stronger interactions created by the divalent cations with the carboxylate groups of the polysaccharide derivatives compared to the monovalent ions mainly present in DMEM.

The stability to hydrolytic degradation of ionotropic crosslinked hydrogels was investigated by evaluating the weight loss of the samples after programmed incubation times. As reported in Figure 6a, each investigated sample shows no significant differences in the recovered weight % as a function of incubation time from day 7 to day 21, suggesting a prolonged stability of each sample during time, at least in vitro. In fact, the initial weight loss observed after 7 days of incubation for all investigated samples is probably attributable to the loss of hydrogel fragments formed during the drying procedure which are eliminated after the first days of incubation. This loss is more marked for the undoped hydrogel (60% and 50% of the weight recovered for samples polymerized with 0.1 M CaCl₂ and DMEM, respectively) while it significantly decreases with increasing HAp and β -TCP concentration, further confirming that

Figure 5. SEM micrographs of cross-sectioned a–c) GG-C₁₈, d–f) GG-C₁₈ 1% NPs, and g–i) GG-C₁₈ 10% NPs a,d,e) freeze dried hydrogel untreated and cured with b,e,h) DMEM or c,f,i) CaCl₂ 0.1 m. Magnification 1000x (15 kV). Scale bar 80 μm.

these nanoparticles inorganic compounds have a structuring effect on hydrogels.

As expected, samples containing HAp and β -TCP and cured with CaCl₂ 0.1 m show higher recovered weight % values than DMEM cured samples demonstrating that ionotropic crosslinking with divalent cations is more effective in preserving most of the integrity of the hydrogels ($p < 0.05$).

Thanks the combined effect of ionotropic crosslinking and inorganic nanoparticles, along with the intrinsic properties of GG-C₁₈ to create stable 3D networks in physiological conditions due to the hydrophobic interactions of the alkyl chains,^[15] stable hydrogels that could potentially be implanted in the bone defect have been produced.

2.4. Cytocompatibility, Cell Encapsulation, and Viability Studies

Hydrogels cytocompatibility was investigated by studying the viability of human dermal fibroblasts (NHDF, Lonza) cultured for 24 h in the presence of hydrogels. The samples were cured in both DMEM and CaCl₂ before being kept in indirect contact with

the cells. Results in **Figure 7** show that the viability of cells cultured in the presence of all the investigated samples was highly comparable with that of control cells cultured without hydrogels demonstrating that samples did not release toxic agents in the culture medium.

MC3T3-E1 preosteoblasts were used as model cells to carry out a preliminary investigation of the cytocompatibility of GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels and to study the influence of the encapsulation procedure on cell viability. The peculiar viscoelastic properties of GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels allowed, before ionotropic crosslinking, to mix the polymeric systems with the dispersion of MC3T3-E1 preosteoblasts at room temperature and to inject the cellular constructs into a 24-well culture plate using a 1 mL sterile plastic syringe. These cell containing hydrogels were then cured with sterile CaCl₂ 0.1 m and maintained in culture conditions with DMEM or treated directly with the culture medium.

As shown in Figure 7a,b after 3 days of culture, no dead cells were visible for all samples tested, which means that the mixing procedure and the physicochemical and rheological properties of the hydrogels are compatible with cell viability. No significant differences in cell viability were observed at day 3 between

Figure 6. Degradation profiles of hydrogels after different times of incubation in a) DMEM or cured in CaCl₂ and incubated in b) DMEM. Data are reported as mean value ± standard deviation. Asterisks denoted significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 7. Cytocompatibility of GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels on NHDF by MTS assays. Data are shown as mean ± s.e.m. ($n = 6$; three independent replicates)

cured and uncured samples with CaCl₂. This aspect is particularly important as it would make it possible to use GG-C₁₈ hydrogels as delivery systems for viable cells that could stimulate and accelerate bone regeneration. All investigated hydrogels cultured in DMEM without CaCl₂ treatment show only viable cells at all investigated time points. The MTS test reveals that for the undoped hydrogel there is a significant increase in cell viability between day 7 and day 14, which means that cells can proliferate in this hydrogel. On the other hand, in GG-C₁₈ 1% NP and GG-C₁₈ 10% NP the cell viability of the hydrogels remains practically constant throughout the incubation period. Interestingly, curing with CaCl₂ 0.1 M has a detrimental effect on cell viability, as can be seen from the MTS test results (Figure 7d). In particular, cell viability only increased slightly for the nanoparticle free GG-C₁₈ hydrogel between day 3 and day 7 and shows a significant reduction after 14 days of incubation for all samples tested ($p < 0.05$). This could be attributable to the increased stiffness and more compact structure (see Figure 5) conferred on hydrogels by ionotropic crosslinking with divalent ions which could hinder the diffusion of nutrients into constructs and cause cell death.

2.5. Dexamethasone and SDF-1 α Loading and Release Study

Once injected, a hydrogel designed to enable bone regeneration should be able to support the release of osteoinductive molecules that accelerate the production of new bone matrix or molecules capable of recruiting nearby stem cells to enhance potential tissue regeneration. Here Dexamethasone and SDF-1 α were chosen as osteoinductive and chemoattractive effectors, respectively.^[38]

Release studies have shown that injectable GG-C₁₈ hydrogels could be useful as delivery systems for these bioactive substances. In fact, all the samples tested were able to prolong the release of

Figure 8. Live/dead assay of MC3T3-E1 preosteoblasts encapsulated into GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels cultured in a) DMEM and hydrogels cured in CaCl₂ 0.1 M and cultured in b) DMEM. Representative merged fluorescent micrographs of live (green) and dead (red) cells seeded after 3, 7, and 14 days of cell culture are reported. Scale bars 20 μ m. Values of absorbance at 492 nm obtained from MTS assay for cell containing GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels cultured in c) DMEM or cured in CaCl₂ 0.1 M and cultured in d) DMEM after 3, 7, and 14 days in normal cell culture medium. (* p < 0.05 and ** p < 0.01).

Dexamethasone for more than 3 days. A lower burst effect was recorded for hydrogels loaded with nanoparticles according to a more significant effect at higher dopant concentration. This influence exerted by the nanoparticles suggests a possible drug interaction with HAp and/or β -TCP resulting in a delay in drug diffusion.

However, the release profiles were almost overlapping and no significant differences were noted when comparing the studied samples (Figure 8a).

A more pronounced retention effect was observed for SDF-1 α as clearly evident from Figure 8b. It is likely to suppose that the absorption of bioactive protein onto the surface of hydrophilic nanoparticles slow down the release from the hydrated hydrogel network. This effect could be particularly interesting since would endow the hydrogel with a prolonged cell recruiting effect that could be crucial for the regeneration of the bone defect. It is not trivial to highlight that the encapsulation process did not cause degradation of the bioactive protein.

3. Conclusions

Here we produced injectable hydrogels starting from the aqueous dispersion of the GG derivative called GG-C₁₈ with optimal vis-

coelastic properties given by the sol-gel transition of GG induced by the temperature and by the lipophilic interactions between the pendant octadecyl chains. Aqueous dispersions of GG-C₁₈ give rise to the formation of reversible hydrogels containing nanoparticulate osteoinductive dopants having a structuring effect on the samples without hindering their injectability profile. GG-C₁₈ undergoes ionotropic crosslinking in saline media to form stable hydrogels with improved viscoelastic properties compared to the temperature induced hydrogels. We demonstrated that crosslinking with 0.1 M CaCl₂ allows for the formation of compact hydrogels that have undergone a gradual decrease in elastic modulus when incubated in cell culture medium due to depletion of divalent cations from the ionotropic crosslinked polymer network. On the contrary, using DMEM as a curing medium, a gradual increase in the elastic properties of hydrogels containing HAp and β -TCP has been observed. Preliminary biological studies have revealed that GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels can encapsulate viable preosteoblastic cells and support their viability over time when cured under physiological conditions. Finally, loading and release studies of Dexamethasone and SDF-1 α have shown that it is possible to produce medicated injectable systems capable of controlling the release of osteogenic molecules in the healing bone due to the presence of inorganic nanoparticles.

Figure 9. a). Dexamethasone and **b)** SDF-1 α release profile from GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels incubated in DPBS pH 7.4 at 37 °C.

We believe that, in light of these promising results, GG-C₁₈ hydrogels could potentially be useful for filling minor bone defects (such as in nonload bearing bones) and stimulating the formation of new bone.

4. Experimental Section

Materials and Methods: Gelrite (GG), octadecylamine (C₁₈-NH₂), tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (TBA-OH), bis(4-nitrophenyl)carbonate (4-NPBC), diethyl ether, ethanol (EtOH), acetone, dimethylsulfoxide anhydrous (DMSO), Dowex 50WX8 hydrogen form, sodium hydroxide (NaOH), tetramethylammonium chloride (TMACl), hydroxyapatite nanoparticles (HAp, 200 nm), β -tricalcium phosphate nanoparticles (β -TCP, 200 nm), dexamethasone sodium phosphate (DEX), SDF-1 α (CXCL12, murine recombinant), live dead double staining kit, Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM) fetal bovine serum (FBS), penicillin-streptomycin, glutamine, and amphotericin B were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Italy). MTS reagent (CellTiter 96 AQueous One Solution Cell Proliferation Assay) was purchased from Promega. Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) was performed using a system equipped with a pump system, a 2410 refractive index detector, all purchased from Waters (TA Instruments – Waters S.p.A., Italy). GG samples were eluted by using a PolySep-GFC-P4000 column, with a flow of 0.6 mL min⁻¹, and a column temperature of 35 °C (± 1).

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H-NMR) spectra were recorded using a Bruker AC-300 instrument operating at 300.12 MHz. Rheological analysis was performed with a DHR-2 TA Instruments Trios (TA Instruments – Waters S.p.A., Italy). Fluorescence spectroscopy was performed by using a Shimadzu RF-5301PC spectrofluorophotometer. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were performed using a DSC/TGA 131 EVO instrument (by SETARAM Instr.). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis was conducted using a Phenom XL by Alfatex microscope operating at 5 kV. Customized panels for Luminex (ProcartaPlex) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA).

Synthesis of GGm-C₁₈ Derivative: GG derivative at lower molecular weight and its tetrabutyl ammonium salt, named GG-TBA, were prepared following a procedure reported elsewhere with slight modifications.^[15]

In particular, GG-TBA (200 mg) was dispersed in DMSO (17.6 mL) at 40 °C to obtain a final concentration of 1% w/v. A solution of 4-NPBC (13.72 mg) in DMSO (2.4 mL) was then added (molar ratio between 4-NPBC and GG repetitive units equal to 0.1). After 4 h, an appropriate amount of C₁₈-NH₂ was added to obtain a molar ratio C₁₈-NH₂/4-NPBC, equal to 1.2; the temperature was raised to 60 °C and the reaction was carried out for further 24 h. The work out of the reaction was accomplished by adding NaCl saturated solution (0.2 mL) to the reaction flask. The product was precipitated with an excess of diethyl ether/ethylacetate (1:1 v/v) and washed with hot diethyl ether/ethyl acetate, ethanol/water (8:2 v/v), absolute ethanol and finally with acetone. GG-C₁₈ was finally dried under vacuum at room temperature.

The functionalization degree in C₁₈ moieties, calculated by means of ¹H-NMR analysis (see the Supporting Information), was 14 \pm 0.5 mol%.

Hydrogels Production: The hydrogels were produced by dispersing 3% w/v GG-C₁₈ in water by autoclaving procedure (121 °C for 15 min) in the presence or absence of different quantities of HAp and β -TCP nanoparticles (HAp: β -TCP weight ratio 1:1).

Obtained dispersions were cooled at 40 °C and placed (500 μ L) into Nunc Polycarbonate Cell Culture Inserts for 24 well plate with 8 μ m pore size by means of 1 mL syringe. Three batches of samples, labeled as GG-C₁₈, GG-C₁₈ 1% NPs, and GG-C₁₈ 10% NPs, were produced by adding respectively 0%, 1%, or 10% of nanoparticles with respect to the GG-C₁₈ weight. The ionically crosslinked hydrogels were prepared by immersing the obtained samples in 0.1 M CaCl₂ buffer or DMEM for 1 h.

Rheological Characterization: For thermal-rheological experiments, GG-C₁₈, GG-C₁₈ 1% NPs, GG-C₁₈ 10% NPs dispersions, obtained as described in Section 4.2 were analyzed in the temperature range between 5 and 50 °C using a parallel plate geometry with radial groove and with an 8 mm diameter upper plate. Dispersions were kept in a water bath at 50 °C until the analysis was performed. The temperature dependence of storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') was observed by cooling the samples from 50 °C to 5 °C at a rate of 2 °C min⁻¹ by applying a constant strain of 1.5% and a frequency of 0.159 Hz (1 rad s⁻¹). Samples were previously equilibrated at a temperature of 50 °C for 60 s and a pre-shear of 0.1 rad s⁻¹ for 10 s was performed. A layer of silicone oil was applied to minimize water evaporation during measurement. The linear viscoelastic region was preliminarily assessed by strain sweep experiments applying a constant frequency of 0.159 Hz at 5, 37, and 50 °C and it was found in the range of 0.8–13% of deformation at 5 and 37 °C and in the range of 1.5–13% of

deformation at 50 °C. The injectability of nanocomposite polymeric dispersions was studied by evaluating G' and G'' yield stress and recovery at 25 °C. In particular, yield stress was measured applying a logarithmic flow ramp with a shear stress ramp between 10 and 1000 Pa (measurement duration: 5 min) while rotational recovery was evaluated by applying a low stress (10 Pa) for 200 s, followed by a high stress (1000 Pa) for 200 s and finally a low stress (10 Pa) for 200 s applying a constant frequency of 0.1 Hz.

For frequency sweep measurements polymeric dispersions were first ionically crosslinked using DMEM buffer or CaCl_2 0.1 M for 1 h, then both incubated for further 14 days in DMEM buffer. Samples were maintained at 37 °C refreshing the medium every two days. Viscoelastic properties were evaluated at 37 °C by performing *frequency sweep* measurements in the range 0.01–10 Hz by applying a constant strain of 1.5%. In particular, the viscoelastic linear region was preliminarily detected through *strain sweep* experiments (strain 0.013–13%, at 0.159 Hz). The measurement gap was set at 300 μm for all analyses and the excess of sample was carefully removed before starting the experiment. All experiments were carried out in triplicate.

Physicochemical Characterization: Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermo-gravimetric analysis, in vitro degradation profile and SEM characterization were performed on ionically crosslinked samples. In particular, after crosslinking with DMEM or CaCl_2 0.1 M, hydrogels were briefly washed with water in order to remove exceeding salts and freeze-dried.

Scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analyses were performed under nitrogen flow (1 mL min^{-1}) using dried sample (5 mg) placed into an aluminum crucible. An empty pan was used as a reference. A scan rate of 10 °C min^{-1} was employed to heat the samples from 25 to 500 °C.

For morphological analyzes, freeze dried samples were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). For the determination of the degradation profile, freeze dried ionically crosslinked hydrogels (both with DMEM and CaCl_2), were carefully weighed and incubated in DMEM at 37 °C under gentle stirring. At scheduled times points (7, 14, and 21 days), samples were rapidly washed in ultra pure water, freeze-dried and weighed.

The degradation of the samples was expressed as weight recovered percentage ($W_r\%$), calculated as

$$W_r\% = W_f/W_i \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_f is the weight of recovered sample (final weight) at each time point and W_i is its initial weight. Each experiment was performed in triplicate.

Cytocompatibility Studies: Cylindrical hydrogels (from 500 μL of gelling solution) produced as already described and cured both in DMEM and CaCl_2 were freeze dried and sterilized by UV irradiation at 254 nm for at least 1 hour (30 min per side) using a 125 W UV-lamp.

NHDF were cultured in DMEM supplemented with fetal bovine serum (10% v/v), glutamine, penicillin-streptomycin solution, and amphotericin and cultured at 37 °C and 5% CO_2 atmosphere. Cells were seeded in 48 wells plate (2×10^4 cells per each well) and cultured for 24 h. At this point, hydrogels were inserted into each culture well in order to make them float in the culture medium. Cells viability was investigated through MTS sample after further 24 h of culture following the manufacturer's specifications. Cell's viability was expressed as % of control viability that is cells cultured without hydrogels.

Cell Encapsulation and Viability Studies: MC3T3-E1 preosteoblast cells cultured at 37 °C, 5% CO_2 with a humidified atmosphere in DMEM supplemented with 10% v/v of FBS, 1% v/v of penicillin–streptomycin solution, 1% v/v of glutamine solution and 0.1% v/v amphotericin B solution, were used for biological studies. After trypsinization, cells were counted, re-suspended in DMEM and loaded in a 1 mL syringe. Polymeric dispersions were prepared as already described and loaded into 1 mL syringes. Cell encapsulation took place by gentle mixing of the cell suspension and polymer dispersions through an appropriate syringe-syringe coupler. After mixing, 200 μL (cell density of 1×10^5 cells mL^{-1}) of each cell-loaded dispersion were deposited on 24-wells plate. Obtained constructs were both cured with sterile CaCl_2 0.1 M for 1 h and immersed into DMEM or into the culture medium without saline solution treatment. After 3, 7, and 14 days,

cell viability test was carried out by MTS test following the manufacturer instructions. Experiments were performed in triplicate.

A live and dead double staining assay (calcein AM and ethidiumhomodimer-III (EthDIII)) was also performed, following the manufacturer instruction, to visualize cells encapsulated into GG-C₁₈ based hydrogels at scheduled days of culture. Images were obtained by fluorescence microscope Zeiss Axio Vert.

Dexamethasone and SDF-1 α Loading and Release Study: GG-C₁₈, GG-C₁₈ 1% NPs, GG-C₁₈ 10% NPs dispersions (at 40 °C) were singly mixed with the proper amount of Dexamethasone sodium phosphate (Dex) to obtain a final weight concentration equal to 1% (w/w) respect to the GG-C₁₈. After loading, the hydrogels were allowed to cool to room temperature. Cylindrical pieces of hydrogels were then placed on Nunc inserts for 24 well plate and incubated in DPBS pH 7.4 at 37 °C. Dex release was followed for further 72 h; at predetermined time points, 100 μL of buffer was withdrawn and replaced with fresh aliquots of DPBS. The amount of released Dex was measured by UV-VIS spectroscopy.

For SDF-1 α , the same loading procedure as the Dex was used. 100 μL of SDF-1 α loaded dispersions were incubated with DPBS (1 mL) and its release was followed for 72 h. At each time point, medium (0.5 mL) was withdrawn for SDF-1 α quantification and replaced with fresh DPBS aliquots. The amount of SDF-1 α released from the hydrogel at each time point was measured by Luminex multi analyte profiling (xMAP) technology, and expressed as pg mL^{-1} .

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis for significance was performed by means of Student's *t*-test assuming two-tailed distribution and unequal variance. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Research data are not shared.

Keywords

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